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TEACHING APTITUDE AMONG B.Ed. TRAINEES: A STUDY

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The present study investigated the aptitude of B.Ed. trainees towards teaching. The objectives of the study were: (i) To compare teaching aptitude of male and female B.Ed students. (ii) To compare teaching aptitude of B.Ed. students of Arts and Science stream. (iii) To compare teaching aptitude of B.Ed students studying in self-financed and government aided institutions. The study was conducted on a sample of 100 B.Ed students of Allahabad city. Teaching Aptitude Test developed by S. S. Dahiya and L. C. Singh was used as a tool for the study. t-ratio was computed for the analysis of the data. The findings of the study revealed- (i) There is no significant difference in teaching aptitude of male and female B.Ed. students. (ii) There is no significant difference in teaching aptitude B.Ed. students of Arts and Science stream. (iii) There is no significant difference in teaching aptitude of B.Ed. students studying in self-financed and government aided institutions.

Aptitude is an important characteristic of an individual which can predict the future success or failure of an individual in an occupation. Aptitude is a specific ability or a specific capacity distinct from general intellectual ability, which helps an individual to acquire degree of proficiency or achievement in a specific field. Traxler (1957) is of the view that aptitude is a condition, a quality or a set of qualities in an individual which is indicative of the probable extent to which he will be able to acquire under suitable training, some knowledge, skill, understanding to do certain things. If an individual has an aptitude towards something then there are chances of his/her success in that particular area. In the present scenario, researches had provided substantial evidence regarding the fact that teacher aptitude has declined over the past generations. Teacher

aptitude refers to the fact that it is a condition or set of characteristics that estimates the extent to which the individual will profit from the specified course of training, or forecast the quality of his/her achievement in training. Quality education depends on quality teachers. Teacher quality is the key factor affecting pupil performance. According to Châu, (1996), in the initial stages of education, and especially in the rural areas, the quality of education depends on the quality of teachers. Teachers are trained in the teacher-training institutions, thus the teacher-training institutions have an important role to play in this regard. But the teacher education institutes are not magical factories that'll produce the living encyclopedias in merely one or two years. They can only train and polish the trainees and this can be done only when they will have an aptitude for teaching. Studies on teaching aptitude have shown that elementary teacher educators have more teaching aptitude as compared to secondary teacher educators (Tasleema & Hamid, 2012). Chugh (2012) reported that teacher trainees of Haryana have average teaching aptitude. Fatime and Humaira (2011) found that B.Ed. trainees have above average teaching aptitude. Teaching aptitude is found to be significantly correlated with teacher effectiveness (Beena, 1995; Vyas, 1990), mental ability (Chug, 2012); teaching success (Kukretti, 1999), attitude towards teaching, (Vashishta, 1973), general intelligence (Thakkur, 1977; Banerjy, 1956); creativity (Jain, 1992); academic achievement (Kohlman & Saini, 1989) although no correlation was found with previous educational qualifications, age (Chug, 2012). Raval (2012) reported no significant effect of sex, SES and area on teaching aptitude among primary teacher trainees.

On the light of the above discussion, the present study is an attempt to investigate teaching aptitude among B.Ed. trainees.

Objectives:

The objectives of the study were as follows-

1. To compare teaching aptitude of male and female B.Ed students.

2. To compare teaching aptitude of B.Ed. students of Arts and Science stream.
3. To compare teaching aptitude of B.Ed students studying in self-financed and government aided institutions.

Hypotheses:

To achieve the above mentioned objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated and tested-

1. There is no significant difference in teaching aptitude of male and female B.Ed. students.
2. There is no significant difference in teaching aptitude of B.Ed. students of Arts and Science stream
3. There is no significant difference in teaching aptitude of B.Ed. students studying in self-financed and government aided institutions.

Methodology:

The study was conducted on a sample of 100 B.Ed students of Allahabad city. Teaching Aptitude Test developed by S. S. Dahiya and L. C. Singh was used as a tool for the study. t-ratio was computed for the analysis of the data.

Result & Discussion

Table 1

Mean, S.D. and t-ratio showing the difference in teaching aptitude of male and female B.Ed students

Groups	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Male	50	30.66	5.165	1.072
Female	50	31.74	4.911	

Observation of Table 1 shows that the value of t-ratio (=1.072) is not significant at .05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis that ‘There is no significant difference in teaching aptitude of male and female B.Ed. students’ can be accepted. It means that male and female B.Ed students have similar teaching aptitude. Similar were the findings of Chugh (2012), Fatima and Humaira (2011) and Sharma (1984). They also reported no difference in teaching aptitude of male and female teacher- trainees. However, findings of Ganoje (2011) and Pandey (1980) were contradictory. Ganoje found that female trainees have teaching aptitude than male trainees while Pandey reported that as compared to female trainees, male trainees have higher teaching aptitude..

Table 2

Mean, S.D. and t-ratio showing the difference in teaching aptitude of B.Ed students of Arts and Science stream

Groups	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Arts	43	30.51	5.133	1.188
Science	57	31.72	4.956	

Perusal of Table 2 reveals that the value of t-ratio (=1.188) is not significant at .05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis that ‘There is no significant difference in teaching aptitude of B.Ed. students of Arts and Science stream’ can be accepted. It means that B.Ed students of Arts and Science stream do not differ from one another on teaching aptitude. Contradictory were the findings of Ganoje (2011). She reported significant difference in teaching aptitude between D.T.Ed. trainees of science & Arts Streams.

Table 3

**Mean, S.D. and t-ratio showing the difference in teaching aptitude of B.Ed students
studying in self-financed and government aided institutions**

Groups	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Self-financed	50	31.04	5.170	0.316
Government aided	50	31.36	4.960	

Table 3 reveals that the value of t-ratio ($=0.316$) is not significant at .05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis that 'There is no significant difference in teaching aptitude of B.Ed. students studying in self-financed and government aided institutions' can be accepted. It means that B.Ed students studying in self-financed and government aided institutions have equal teaching aptitude. However, Ganoje (2011) found that teaching aptitude of D.T.Ed. trainees belonging to Government colleges is better than that of trainees of Non government colleges. Pandey (1980) reported that B.Ed students of private colleges have better teaching aptitude than their counterparts studying in government colleges.

Thus, it can be concluded that there is no difference in teaching aptitude of male and female; Arts stream and Science stream B.Ed. students. It was also found that B.Ed. students studying in self-financed and government aided institutions have similar teaching aptitude.

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